

Archaeologists in Gaza

STUDY AN ENDANGERED HERITAGE

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Résumé : Être archéologue à Gaza : étudier un patrimoine en péril

À Gaza, la recherche archéologique et historique et la sauvegarde du patrimoine local sont des enjeux de taille, menacés à la fois par un conflit qui s'enlise, mais aussi par l'expansion permanente d'une population grandissante. Étudier l'histoire de ce territoire suppose une certaine prise de risques : les bombardements y sont réguliers, menaçant aussi bien les hommes que les sites.

Gaza est une cité millénaire, à l'histoire riche et ancienne ; certaines zones de son territoire ont pu être fouillées par une équipe franco-palestinienne de 1995 à 2012, malgré des interruptions (2006-2010) et de nombreux aléas (construction de bâtiments sur les zones de chantier, destruction de certains sites). Les informations collectées composent aujourd'hui un matériel inédit, dont les sources sont désormais inaccessibles voire disparues.

A l'exemple de l'Apollon de Gaza découvert en 2013, nombre d'objets archéologiques y sont pillés, déplacés, vendus ou détruits, en fonction de leur importance supposée, de leur valeur marchande et de la situation politique. Les collections privées de Gaza constituent alors, face au pillage du patrimoine local, l'occasion pour les archéologues et les historiens d'approfondir leur quête.

Travailler sur place nécessite une adaptation parfois complexe – en utilisant les moyens du bord, souvent réduits – et une grande rigueur afin de collecter le maximum d'informations possibles. Ainsi le trésor de Rafah, découvert en 2010, n'a pu être étudié que durant deux mois en août 2012 et 2013, avant que l'accès à Gaza ne soit interdit. Le travail sur les matériaux de fouilles est désormais limité faute d'accès au territoire.

Le travail archéologique exécuté sur place doit être rigoureux et intense ; s'y ajoute une collecte d'informations permanente et ininterrompue. Ces informations permettent aux chercheurs, une fois revenus de leur séjour, d'exploiter les données recueillies et d'éclairer un peu plus nos connaissances pour ce territoire, à la fois pour éviter la destruction de pans entiers de l'Histoire, mais aussi pour rendre à la population de Gaza son passé.

Mots-clefs : Apollon, Conflit israélo-palestinien, histoire ancienne, monde perse, monde grec ancien, monde romain, numismatique, pillage, archéologie d'urgence.

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Abstract : In Gaza, the whole historical and patrimonial dimension is a major challenge, both by the conflict situation and by the poor and constantly expanding population, greedy for land. To work on its ancient history supposes the taking of personal risks : the bombardments are permanent there, threatening the men as well as the sites.

As the example of the Gaza's Apollo discovered in 2013, many archaeological objects are looted, displaced, sold or destroyed, depending on their importance or value. In this regard, the private collections of Gaza are a wealth and an opportunity for archaeologists and historians in their quest. Place of a rich and ancient history, some sites in the neighbourhood of Gaza were excavated by a French-Palestinian team from 1995 to 2012, with a long interruption (2006-2010) and many hazards (construction of buildings on the excavation site, destruction of sites). The material collected gives plenty new informations, through the archaeological discoveries which alas could, in the peculiar conditions of Gaza, easily disappear.

Working on site requires full adaptation - using the means of the edge, often reduced - and a great rigor in order to collect as much information as possible. Thus the Rafah treasure, discovered in 2010, could only be studied for two months in August 2012 and 2013, before access was forbidden. The work on EBAF (Ecole Biblique et Archéologique Française de Jérusalem) excavation materials was limited due to a restraint access to the territory.

It is both flexible and adaptable work that needs to be done on site, coupled with ongoing, uninterrupted information gathering. These gathered informations allow the researchers, once returned from the stay, to exploit the collected data and enlighten knowledge toward this territory, both to avoid the destruction of whole areas of History, and to give back to the Gazaeans, a piece of their hidden past.

Keywords : Apollo, Israeli-Palestinian Conflict, Ancient History, Persian World, Greek World, Roman World, Numismatics, Looting, Emergency Archeology.

ملخص / پوخته / خلاصه

علماء الآثار في غزة: دراسة التراث المهدد بالخطر

في غزة، يعد البحث الأثري والتاريخي وحماية التراث المحلي من القضايا الرئيسية التي يهددها كل من الصراع، والتوسع الدائم في عدد السكان المتزايد. تفترض دراسة تاريخ هذه الأرض وجود قدر معين من المخاطرة فيما يخص التفجيرات المستمرة التي تهدد الرجال والمواقع. غزة مدينة عمرها آلاف الأعوام، ولها تاريخ غني وقديم. قام فريق فرنسي-فلسطيني بالتنقيب في بعض المناطق في أراضيها من عام 1995 إلى عام 2012، وذلك على الرغم من الانقطاعات (2006-2010) والعديد من المخاطر (تشديد المباني في مواقع البناء وتدمير بعض المواقع). المعلومات التي تم جمعها اليوم تتكون من مواد جديدة غير منشورة والتي أضحت مصادرها غير قابلة للوصول أو أنها اختفت.

على غرار مثال أبولو غزة الذي تم اكتشافه في عام 2010، يتم نهب أو تهجير أو بيع أو تدمير العديد من اللقى الأثرية، اعتماداً على أهميتها المفترضة وقيمتها السوقية والوضع السياسي. تشكل المجموعات الخاصة في غزة، بمواجهة نهب التراث المحلي، فرصة لعلماء الآثار والمؤرخين لتعميق بحثهم. يتطلب العمل في الموقع تكيفاً معقداً في بعض الأحيان - باستخدام إمكانيات ضعيفة، وغالباً ما تكون غير كافية، وبضغط شديد من أجل جمع أكبر قدر ممكن من المعلومات. وبالتالي، فإن كنز رفح، الذي اكتشف عام 2010، تم دراسته خلال مدة شهرين في آب 2012 و 2013 وذلك قبل حظر الدخول إلى غزة. العمل على نتائج التنقيبات محدود الآن بسبب عدم إمكانية الوصول إلى الأرض.

يجب أن يكون العمل الأثري المنجز في الموقع دقيقاً ومكثفاً، بالإضافة إلى المجموعة الدائمة وغير المنقطعة من المعلومات. تتيح هذه المعلومات للباحثين، بمجرد العودة من إقامتهم، استخدام البيانات التي تم جمعها وإلقاء مزيد من الضوء على معرفتنا لهذه الأرض، وذلك لتجنب تدمير مناطق كاملة من التاريخ، وأيضاً لإعادة الماضي إلى أهل غزة. الكلمات المفتاحية: أبولو، الصراع الإسرائيلي الفلسطيني، التاريخ القديم، العالم الفارسي، العالم اليوناني القديم، العالم الروماني، النميات، النهب، علم الآثار الطارئ.

زانایانی شویته‌وار له غزه: لیکۆلینه‌وه‌ی توراسی هه‌ره‌شه‌ی تیچوونیان له سه‌ره

له غزه، توێژینه‌وه‌ی شویته‌واری و میژووی وه پاراستنی توراسی ناوخۆی بابه‌تیکی سه‌ره‌کبه کها جه‌نگی ده‌بێته هی مه‌ترسی رووخانی، وه له‌گه‌ڵ ته‌وه‌شدا به هۆی زیاردبوونی به‌رده‌وای ژماره‌ی دانشتوان. لیکۆلینه‌وه له‌ ناوچه‌یه‌دا ده‌خاته مه‌ترسیه‌وه: ته‌قینه‌وه به‌دوای یه‌که‌که‌ندا ده‌بنه مه‌ترسی بۆ سه‌ر مرۆڤ و ناوچه‌کان. غزه شارێکه ته‌مه‌نی هه‌زاران ساڵه، وه میژوویکی دۆله‌مه‌ند و کۆنی هیه، تیی فه‌ره‌نسی فه‌له‌ستینی به‌هه‌لکۆلینی هه‌ندی ناوچه له سالانی 1995 تا 2012، هه‌رچه‌نده بچران له کارکردندا هه‌بووه (2006-2010) له گه‌ڵ هه‌بوونی زۆر مه‌ترسی (درووست کردنی بینایه له ناوچه‌کانی بینایه و رووخاندنی هه‌ندی ناوچه‌ی دیکه). ئه‌و زانیاریانه‌ی که‌وا ئیستا کۆکراوه‌ته‌وه له ماده‌ی نوی پیکهاتوون وه سه‌رچاوه‌کانیان له ئیستادا په‌سه‌ند نیه بۆ گه‌یشتن یا هه‌تا که له ده‌ستدانه‌دا.

وه‌ک دۆزینه‌وه‌ی ته‌پۆلوی غزه که‌وا له 2013 دا دۆزرایه‌وه، کۆمه‌لێک پاشماوه‌ی شویته‌واری دزران و تالان کران یا فرۆشران و زۆرشیان رووخان و تیکچوون، به و پێی که‌وا گرنگن و نرخی بازاریان هه‌یه له باری سیاسدا. کۆمه‌له‌ تایه‌ته‌کانی غزه بریتین له، رووبه‌رووبوونه‌وه‌ی به تالان بردنی توراسی ناوخۆی، ده‌ره‌فتیک بوو بۆ زانایانی شویته‌وارناس و میژوونووسان بۆ زیاتر قوولبوونه‌وه له توێژینه‌وه‌کانیدا. پۆستی به کاری ده‌ست به‌جی بوو ته‌مه‌ش کارێکی زه‌حمه‌ته له هه‌ندی کاتدا-به‌ به‌کارهێنانی ریگایه‌کی ئاسان، وه زۆرجار که‌مه‌بوو-وه هه‌ول‌دان بۆ کۆکردنه‌وه‌ی زۆرتین زانیاری به پێی پۆستی. وه هه‌وه‌ها، گه‌نجینه‌ی ره‌فا، که‌وا له سالی 2010 دا دۆزرایه‌وه، ته‌نها له دوو مانگدا توانرا دیراسه‌ بکریته له توغستی 2012 و 2013، پێش ئه‌وه‌ی چوون بۆ غزه قه‌ده‌غه بکریته. کارکردن له سه‌ر ماده دۆزراوه‌کان قورس بووه له ئیستا دا له به‌ر ئه‌وه‌ی ناتوانیته‌ بگه‌ین به‌و شویته‌وه.

کاری شویته‌واری ته‌نجامدراو له سه‌ر ناوچه‌کاندا ده‌بێت وورد و چریته، له‌وه زیاتر، کۆمه‌له‌ زانیاریکی به‌رده‌وام و به‌ی بچران بووه. ئه‌م زانیاریانه ریگه‌ خوش ده‌کون بۆ توێژه‌ران، له کاتی گه‌رانه‌وه‌یان بۆ شویته‌واریان، به‌ به‌کارهێنانی زانیاریه‌ کۆکراوه‌کان و زیاتر تیشک خسته‌ سه‌ر زانیاریه‌کامان له سه‌ر ناوچه‌که، وه دوورکه‌وته‌وه‌ی ناوچه‌کان به ته‌واوه‌تی له رووخانی یژووبدا، وه بۆ یۆ گه‌رانه‌وه رابردووه‌ی بۆ هه‌ولاتیانی غزه.

ووشه‌ی ئێپه‌ر: ئاپۆلو، ناکۆکی ئیسراییل و فه‌له‌ستین، میژووی کۆن، جیهانی فارسی، جیهانی یۆنانی کۆن، جیهانی رۆمانی، دراوی، تالان بردن، فریاگوزاری شویته‌واری.

باستانشناسان در غزه: مطالعه میراث فرهنگی در معرض نابودی

در غزه، تحقیقات باستان‌شناسی و تاریخی و حافظت از میراث فرهنگی محلی اهدافی بزرگی اند. میراث فرهنگی این کشور از یکسو توسط جنگ به لجن زاری تبدیل شده و از جانب دیگر توسط رشد مداوم نفوس تهدید میگردد. مطالعه تاریخ این قلمرو چالش‌های را با خود به همراه دارد، بطور نمونه: بمباردمان مداوم تهدید جدی هم برای جمعیت و ساحات باستانی بشمار می‌رود. غزه شهری با هزاران سال قدمت، تاریخ غنی و قدیم است؛ بعضی از نقاط این قلمرو در سالهای ۱۹۹۵ تا ۲۰۱۲ میلادی؛ با وجودی وقفه‌های سالهای (2010-2006) میلادی و خطرات دیگری چون (ساخت و ساز روی ساحات باستانی و تخریب بعضی از ساحات) توسط تیمی مشترک فرانسه - فلسطینی حفاری گردید. امروز معلومات گردآوری شده این کاوش‌ها منابع نادر؛ غیر قابل دسترس و حتی ناپدید شده‌اند.

بطور مثال، تعداد زیادی از اشیای باستانی، که در آپولون غزه در سال 2013 میلادی کشف گردیدند، نظر به اهمیت فرضی، ارزش مادی و حالات نظامی؛ غارت، انتقال، تخریب و به فروش رسیدند. در مقابل، کلکسیون‌های شخصی غزه، فرصتی برای مؤرخین و باستان‌شناسان است، تا به تحقیقات خویش پردازند. کارکردن در روی ساحه ضرورت به سازشی دارد، که بعضی از اوقات مغلق اند. بطور نمونه باید با امکانات محدود، گاهاً ناچیز - و با دقت بیشتر به جمع‌آوری حداکثر اطلاعات ممکن پرداخت.

همچنان، گنجینه رخ که در سال ۲۰۱۰ میلادی کشف گردید، فقط در جریان ماه‌های اوت/اگست ۲۰۱۲ و ۲۰۱۳ میلادی مورد مطالعه قرار گرفت؛ قبل ازینکه ورود به غزه ممنوع گردد. بعد از این زمان، تحقیق و دسترسی به اشیای که از کاوش‌ها بدست آمده؛ بخاطر عدم ورود به این قلمرو محدود باقی مانده اند.

تحقیقات باستان‌شناسی، که در ساحه اجراً میشوند باید دقیق، فراگیر و اطلاعات بگونه مداوم و بدون وقفه جمع‌آوری گردند. معلومات جمع‌آوری شده پس از ختم تحقیقات ساحوی برای پژوهشگران اجازه میدهد تا نتایج بیشتری را از بطن این داده‌ها بیرون و روشنایی بیشتری برای شناخت بهتر این قلمرو ارائه نمایند. نتایج این اطلاعات بخاطر جلوگیری از تخریب بخش از تاریخ و احیای دوباره گذشته مردم غزه ضروری پنداشته میشود.

واژه‌های کلیدی: آپولون، منازعه فلسطین-اسرائیل، تاریخ قدیم، امپراتوری پارس، امپراتوری یونان قدیم، امپراتوری روم، سکه‌شناسی، غارت، باستان‌شناسی اضطرابی.

FIG. 1: Excavation sites. Map from HALDIMANN *et al.* 2007, p. 6.

INTRODUCTION

GAZA and its region are now very well known, but much more because of media propaganda about the Israeli-Palestinian conflict and about accusations of terrorism, than for the incredible cultural and archaeological amplitude of its past history.

Yet, in Gaza, historical materials and the cultural heritage are a major issue. Excavations in Gaza and its region over the past century have revealed ancient sites of extraordinary wealth. Gaza, a former Philistine city, is at the center of a region which is a major crossroads of trade between the eastern Mediterranean and the Arab and Egyptian worlds, during the Bronze Age and Iron Age: Tell es Sakkan (1995), Deir el Balah 1972-81), Tell Ruqeish, Tell Ajjul (1931-37), Tell Blakhiyah (1995-2012), are all major sites on the Philistine coast² (fig. 1).

Excavations in the area have been frequently interrupted by the wars of the twentieth century which have opposed the great European powers³. Beginning in 1948, the State of Israel developed a growing archaeological interest for Palestine, but Gaza remained apart from this movement until the 1970s; under occupation, excavations were carried out in the form of preventive archaeology; the results of the excavations and surveys of this period are not always accessible⁴.

However, the peculiar situation in this part of the world did not prevent the beginning of new archaeological excavations, in collaboration between France and Palestine from 1995 onwards. Local antiquities strengthened the preservation of archaeological and historical heritage. In 2006, Hamas' seizure of power in the Gaza Strip resulted in the closure of the region, preventing access to the Gaza Strip, under blockade. This sit-

uation caused the missions to be suspended for a few years. The missions resume from 2010 onwards with the restoration project of the monastic complex of Umm el 'Amr under the direction of René Elter (2010-2014)⁵, additional excavations on the Blakhiyah site and study missions of the material could be carried out in 2013 and 2014, while in the same time, two study missions of the Rafah's Hoard (2010), were made in 2012 and 2013⁶.

During the conflict between Israel and Palestine, and particularly since 2005, research in the Gaza Strip has been considerably slowed down; the consequences of the political conflict take the form of complications or limited access to the territory, while the material found by the first missions, or scattered by the constructions or by looting, remains inaccessible. The discovery and especially the preservation of archaeological documentation is then dependent on the individual actions and those of the Department of Antiquities. The corollary of this conflict is the regular destruction of built-up areas and deserted areas, and consequently the reconstruction of these areas, to which is added the urban extension in formerly deserted areas, often on archaeological sites.

Working on the ancient history of Gaza, from archaeological sources, requires taking into account many parameters, of which conflict is a major factor. Consequently, participation in these missions presupposes an awareness of the risks: personal safety is a real subject, and the work on site requires a scientific, human and material adaptation. [Anecdote - In purely administrative terms, no insurance covers a European who would leave for Gaza without a specific NGO]

2. For a general archaeological History, see STERN 2001.

3. Surveys and excavations : MACKENZIE 1918, GARSTANG 1920, PHYTHIAN-ADAMS 1923a, PHYTHIAN-ADAMS 1923b, PETRIE 1931 ; excavation under Israeli occupation see MAZAR 1992, p. 10-26; then French excavations of EBAF (École Biblique et Archéologique Française) 1995 - 2012 under the direction of Jean-Baptiste Humbert.

4. HUMBERT & SADEK 2000, 40.

5. ELTER 2014.

6. BAUZOU & THEVENIN 2013.

Figure 2: Gaza's Apollo, Photo Credit Hiyam Al-Betar, Gaza, 2013.

1. AN HISTORICAL AND HERITAGE ISSUE

The cultural and heritage issues in Gaza are particularly present. Not a month passes without the discovery or interception of archaeological documents looted or destroyed. The example of the Gaza's Apollo gives an idea of the historical, but also political, stakes.

1.1. The surprises of an antique site: the Apollo of Gaza

1.1.1 Discovery and controversy

During our stay in August 2013, we learned that a bronze statue of Apollo was discovered offshore by a fisherman. We quickly got access to photos that were taken by one of our contacts (Hayam Al Betar). Weighing about 500 kilos for 1,70 meters, it was an unusual object: only three other statues of ancient

bronze of Apollo are known at the present time. Alas it was impossible to see the object: it was in possession of the discoverer's family, who refused any visit (fig. 2).

The discovery of this statue attracted the attention of all European newspapers in the months that followed. The first article on this discovery was published on October 10, 2013, and in February of the following year, the articles on the subject multiplied⁷. Apart from the exceptional aspect of this discovery, was highlighted where and how the statue was found. There was much debate and doubt about the history of the statue. The circumstances of the discovery appeared to be very unlikely, partly because of the appearance of the statue, which did not look like expected, the corrosion created by underwater conservation being invisible on the statue, and partly because of the way the statue was said to be extracted out of the water by a single man⁸.

7. Article of SCUTO 2013 in October (10th) 2013, then Le Monde (ZECCHINI 2014), Le Monde Juif.info (PARTOUCHE 2014), RFI (PARADON 2014), France24 (HAMZA 2014), Géopolis France TV (RIBADEAU DUMAS 2014), Bloomberg businessweek (SILVER 2014).

8. See the articles of conflictantiquities.wordpress.com : HARDY 2013a,b, 2014b,a.

Finally, after weeks of newspapers' articles and various questions, the statue suddenly disappears from the news, even in Gaza itself. After so much publicity, all information concerning the Apollo has dried up, and nothing has emerged since.

1.1.2 Reality of power and archaeological importance

As the journalist Nadéra Bouazza mentioned in an article published in December 2014, more than a year after the actual discovery of the statue, it is the question of the reality of power in Gaza that is exposed through the localization, the future and the conservation of the statue⁹. Permanent threat and local environment dictate the need to limit the available information on Gaza's policy, explaining the opacity regarding the provenance and conservation of the statue. Holder of an historical value, it also carries economic value for its owners. It is probable that without the publicity that was given to him by posting his picture on Ebay, the discovery would never have filtered out of Gaza: how many other objects could have been looted, sold without any filtering details?

None of the journalists nor specialists could have known the provenance of the statue, and when it was discovered in August 2013, my colleague and I, who were then on site, did not get the information. Nevertheless, some local sources have told us that the statue was unearthed by accident in a secret place and absolutely not found in the sea. In order not to divulge the information, a story was invented, avoiding the real discoverers to be put in difficulty. In any case, the emergence of this exceptional statue, and the voluntary opacity concerning its discovery, as well as its disappearance a few months later, are symptomatic of the complex political situation in Gaza. According to our contacts, the statue was partly damaged by the war in 2014; its place of preservation remains unknown. It is now lost to science, and the only information we have is the photographs taken in August 2013.

This statue is a witness of the wealth of archaeological sites in Gaza. It is, in the image of this object, an extraordinary patrimony which is regularly plundered. It is easy to understand that a population subjected to blockade and deprived of everything is in the necessity of finding expedients for its own survival, to such an extent that archaeological objects become financial expedients whose historical or cultural value is only addressed in its political dimension: to assert the demands of one

or the other, or to legitimize a policy or a government¹⁰.

1.2. The recurrent question of looting and the leakage of archaeological heritage

A large number of archaeological objects, often looted for survival reasons, are resold on the black market in Gaza as elsewhere; and then emerge on sale in the antique dealers of Jerusalem without official provenance - or under a false provenance. This trend, well-known in the Middle-East, tends to be amplified by the territorial consequences of the conflict. People need money to survive, and they use archaeological objects to earn more. So actions are necessary to limit the loss.

1.2.1 The action of the Department of Antiquities of Gaza

Regularly, my colleague and I are contacted by agents of the Department of Antiquities in Gaza, with the aim of identifying archaeological objects, mostly seized by police officers. Any type of object is concerned, often small ones, probably easier to hide.

Our contacts send some photos; they at least allow us to have an idea of what can be found in Gaza, but rarely with information about their provenance. The plunderers hardly supply their sources. What proportion of plundered objects reaches us? Many of the objects seized are of a monetary nature, probably because of their small size, easy to hide then sell. It is impossible to know the reason that explains this particular proportion, but it still remains a very interesting indication of the role that Gaza may have had during the ancient periods, especially during the Persian and Hellenistic periods. Many of the currencies found are Alexander's coins or Athenian owls, two large monetary series, as important for antiquity as the dollar is in our contemporary civilization.

1.2.2 Border control and archaeological leakage

In 2013, a hoard of coins of Alexander's staters (about fifty) were found off Gaza, bearing the traces of an underwater stay: each currency was stuck in a sand hull mixed with silver oxide. This hoard was purchased by a local collector. In 2016, the second part of this hoard was found; in addition to the fifty previous currencies, there would be more than 5 000 additional tétradrachmas (fig. 3). The coins are easily identifiable: they are

9. BOUAZZA 2014.

10. The same problem is known for Iraq, during the Golfe war and after ; also for Syria and (too)many other countries. See for example BONIS 2016 ; SINGER 2011.

of the same type, with the same invoice, of similar oxidation. In the absence of a buyer, some of these currencies took the black market route. It is impossible to know how many of these coins there was in the hoard, but we know now that there are at least 5000 coins (now in Canada), and probably some thousands more are still in Gaza. Some of them probably succeeded in crossing the border; four were intercepted by the Israeli authorities, and information about the interception were made public on 16 July 2016¹¹.

This hoard, composed of Alexander III currencies, forms a monetary unit probably struck during the period of Alexander's conquest. For the knowledge of currency movements, the types of currencies used, the destinations of these currencies, allowing

to trace a whole military and commercial network; it is a huge loss that the disappearance of this treasure. It remains to skim the online shops and antique shops to gradually rediscover these currencies that will emerge necessarily at one time or another¹².

Confronted with looting and the disappearance of the historical heritage, the importance of the network of research and the scientific links between researchers, archaeologists and numismatists is fundamental.

Research under these conditions is tainted by adaptations sometimes incongruous to local conditions and geopolitical situation: the conflict makes collaborations very difficult, and requires a permanent documentary watch on the antiquity dealers' websites.

Figure 3: The Alexander hoard, Photo Credit Fadel Al-Otol, Gaza, 2013.

11. ARUTZ SHEVA STAFF 2017; TIMES OF ISRAËL STAFF 2017.

12. THEVENIN & BAUZOU 2019.

Figure 4: The athenian hoard exhibition, Photo Credit Hayam Al-betar, Gaza, 2010.

2. RESEARCH IN A CONFLICT ZONE

The Gaza Strip has been extensively excavated, often unpublished; between 1995 and 2013, several missions of excavations and studies were carried out. The French School of Biblical and Archaeological History has held a prominent place under the direction of Jean-Baptiste Humbert and with the support of the Consulate General of France in Palestine. It was thanks to the unwavering support of the French authorities and the obstinacy of our director of excavations that, despite the difficulties, excavations could be carried out.

2.1. Multiple works and threats

Gaza was the subject of both Israeli and Franco-Palestinian excavations from 1995 to 2005 on the basis of a Franco-Palestinian cooperation agreement, with the creation of an Antiquities Department and training of future local specialists on a building site.

2.1.1 The work of the EBAF

The existing conflict situation has clearly oriented the choice of excavation sites, which have been chosen in the emergency of immovable buildings.

It was following the digging of a sewer collector for a refugee camp that the old tell of the port of Gaza was ripped open, revealing a rich and abundant material, and urging the local authorities to open a preventive site on the area before its destruction, through the building of the Es-Shatteh refugee camp (1995).

The site would have been located on the central part of the tell along the coast. Between the time of the decision and the actual excavations, the refugee camp had been built, and the site was then installed on a still virgin ledge at the edge of the tell, along the newly built road near the beach. The political difficulties associated with the presence in Gaza and its region of a large number of post-Six-Day War refugees, required rapid construction of buildings - despite the archaeological project.

The same year, a planned construction buildings was in-

13. DE MIROCHEDJI 2000; DE MIROCHEDJI & SADEK 2000; DE MIROCHEDJI 2001.

errupted in extremis to save a Bronze Age Tell, hidden under several meters of sand, Tell Es Sakkan, then excavated by P. de Miroschedji (1995)¹³.

From 2005 onwards, the excavations were suspended following the blockade on the Gaza Strip. It was not until 2010 that new excavations and study campaigns were able to resume until 2014. Five sites were opened between 1995 and 2012, in addition to a study mission in 2013.

2.1.2 The actions of the Gaza Antiquities Department for local findings

Permanent constructions in Gaza require enormous amount of sand, and ancient tells are heights where the sand has accumulated for hundreds of years, covering and protecting the sites. It is therefore on these sites that the tons of sand needed for urban expansion are taken. In 2010, the Tell Rafah, located in the extreme south of the Gaza Strip on the border of Egypt, was partly destroyed by shovels. One of them then broke a jar, buried there for over 2000 years, revealing nearly 1,400 silver coins.

This hoard was very quickly seized by the authorities of the Department of Antiquities of Gaza and shown through a special exhibition (fig. 4). Between the discovery and the seizure, nearly 200 coins were taken, which were found, for some, in local private collections, for others on online antiquity dealers' websites. This hoard is exceptional in two ways:

1. The first hoard known of this importance, found in the Gaza Strip,
2. The hoard could have been quickly seized by the local authorities and studied.

16 coins have been found on websites, 22 in private collections, 1218 in the museum of the Gaza Antiquities Department, in Qasr El Pacha. The Ministry of Antiquities has requested the collaboration of European specialists to study the treasure thus secured (photos of work in Qasr). This was the subject of two surveys in 2012 and 2013.

As a result of this discovery, the site was evacuated and placed under the control of the department; local archaeologists have defined three sites; two down the tell, one at its top. The excavations were interrupted following difficulties at the Egyptian border in 2013 and 2014. The study of the hoard is still on course.

2.2. Human and material adaptation

2.2.1 Adapting to human and political constraints

Working in Gaza requires maintaining cordial relations with both sides of the conflict. This is a diplomatic game requiring some adaptation. The simple passage of the border takes time: a complete administrative file on each participant must be filled in, and the permissions are not always granted. This simple passage sometimes takes several months: it is a question of finding an agreement between the official Israeli administrations, the official administrations in Gaza, and the French consulate. It is clear that the latent war situation and the Gaza government's ranking as a terrorist state limits the accessibility of the sites and makes each passage more complex, especially in times of tension (for example 2014-2015).

The conditions and length of stay on the spot, are submitted to the local situation. The Rafah's Hoard, discovered in 2010, has been studied two months in August 2012 and 2013. In 2014, only a short two-week stay was permitted in April, working on the private collection, and a second longer stay was interrupted following the declaration of war on July 7.

2.2.2 The diplomatic constraint – a personal reflexion

It is absolutely necessary to maintain contacts as tight as possible both in the Palestinian area and in the Israeli territories, because the passage through Gaza necessarily involves recurrent contacts with the Israeli authorities (airport, border). From this point of view, it is sometimes difficult to ignore personal feelings in order to emphasize the scientific dimension, and consequently the question of work ethics arises on one side as well as the other: to what extent are science and knowledge acceptable reasons to stay neutral, as a human confronted to endangered lives or a threatening situation? How much are we scientific or ethical while voluntarily staying apart from the conflict? How much are we scientific or ethical, giving an historical value to looted objects, knowing where it is coming from? Could it be more fair not to study it? The questions remain.

2.2.3 Adapt to material constraints

Work on EBAF excavation materials, on the collection or on the hoard was carried out with the tools that were then available on site. Few things can be taken to Gaza, so the equipment has to fit in a suitcase because the passage is only possible by foot. While some of the restoration equipment is transportable (scalpels), everything else must be found on the site. Thus, in order to compensate for the missing restoration tools, it was neces-

sary to build an electrolysis laboratory on site in 2012, which has been used to restore the private collection, to clean some coins from Rafah's hoard and coins from EBAF's excavations in 2012 and 2013.

Electrolysis, as well as chemical restoration baths, were entirely made in Gaza itself, and stayed in the material storage. The cataloguing of coins in the Qasr el Pasha was an opportunity to adapt to local conditions: without suitable equipment, boxes of shoes and hazelnut bags were used to classify each coin. Electricity was only available 6 hours every two days, and it was a generator that allowed us to take photos and use computers in the Qasr el Pacha, and the monetary restoration was done mechanically when electricity was unavailable.

Another example: The stamping of an inscription was the occasion of an experiment. The equipment suitable for this purpose was not found, and the conditions did not permit to search for shops. Therefore, it is with basic products that the inscription was taken: brush of blush, black eye shadow, hairspray, handkerchiefs (fig. 5).

Whatever the material we had to study, photography, restore, it was necessary to gather as much information as possible. Each mission can face a sudden interruption, each information collected is a victory. Each passing year, requests for entry into Gaza become more and more difficult, so that each mission is foreseen with no certainty of realization. Since 2014, none of the previously mentioned projects could be accomplished.

All information from the Rafah's hoard was collected, but the majority of the material from the two EBAF'S excavations, Blakhiyah and Jabbaliyah are still in a warehouse in Gaza, now entrusted to the care of one of our contacts on the spot. We do not know when, or even if, it will be possible to go back and continue the study. Other excavations are nevertheless necessary: as evidenced by the incredible variety and richness of the material, the region is still far from having revealed all its secrets, and the historical and cultural heritage of Gaza is still, for our knowledge of the history of the Middle East and for the inhabitants of this ancient city, a treasure still very little known.

Figure 5: Tools used for coin cleaning in the Qasr el Pacha, Photo Credit Thomas Bauzou, Gaza, 2012.

Figure 6: The destruction of the Tell es Sakkan, Photo Credit Fadel Al-Otol, Gaza, 2017.

3. THE IDENTITY QUESTION IN A WAR CONTEXT

3.1. Destruction and reconstructions: a vicious circle

In Gaza, archaeological research is essentially a matter of emergency: the multiplication of areas under construction clearly threatens major sites, most of which are witnesses of an old and complex History along the coast – even for the ones still occupied (Tell Harubah, the site of ancient Gaza).

3.1.1 Sites at Risk

Tell Rafah, located on the border of Egypt, is a site of regular clashes between the Palestinians in the south of the Gaza Strip and armed Egyptian groups; as all unbuilt areas, it is a spot threatened by psychological bombardments that take place throughout the year in Gaza¹⁴. As for all the other empty territories of the Gaza strip, Tell Rafah is threatened by the growing impact of building construction.

In August 2017, a construction project was established on

the Tell es Sakkan site. This project could have succeeded if the Department of Antiquities of Gaza had not contacted all the archaeologists who formerly worked there; Jean-Baptiste Humbert went to Gaza to warn the authorities about the historical meaning of the site; he presented in detail the discoveries that the site allowed. It was finally thanks to the intervention of the inhabitants of Gaza that the workers were stopped until today (fig.6).

3.1.2 The example of a destructive reconstruction

The destruction of buildings in each war result in reconstruction, necessary for the local population. These reconstructions are nevertheless destructive, each of them requires the digging of foundations that gradually destroys the deep layers of the old tell of Gaza. In April 2016, a building had to be rebuilt; at the time the foundations were dug, the remains of a byzantine church appeared¹⁵. Despite the importance of the newly-revealed site, it was impossible to stop the work in progress,

14. These kind of weapons are created to produce explosions noises, in order to maintain a certain level of fear. They do not create as much damages as real rockets, but still produce a significant blast.

15. EUROPE ISRAËL NEWS 2016.

the Department of Antiquities can't oppose housing, especially when work is already under way. The photos taken by a friend show the remains of the Byzantine church, probably not the only archaeological monument that this building construction has returned to nothingness.

The recurring destruction of the settlements in Gaza, at each war, does not only destroy buildings and lives; they destroy a past, and in doing so, it is an identity, a past and a whole culture that is threatened with extinction. The conflict then became a machine for the mass destruction of heritage, and it was largely thanks to private collectors that the archaeological documentation of Gaza was saved from the destruction of war and from looting.

3.2. Private collections, an answer to the situation?

In this regard, the private collections of Gaza are an opportunity for archaeologists and historians in their quest. Two collectors are known to us in Gaza, one for allowing us to study the objects he had patiently gathered for 25 years; the second let one of our contacts on the spot take some photos of his collection, alas closed to our studies.

3.2.1 The Khoudary Collection

The collection of Mr. Al Khoudary contains thousands of objects, from coins to Christian Cross, columns and capitals, lamps and amphoras ... His collection is today saving a significant part of the heritage of Gaza, a heritage that disappears as destruction, reconstruction or plundering continues.

Mr. Al Khoudary's personal mission is to preserve as much as possible the archaeological and historical heritage of Gaza. Al Khoudary family, long-time gazean inhabitants, is aware of the richness and age of archaeological sites in the Gaza Strip. For twenty-five years he has been buying and collecting all the archaeological objects he has managed to find¹⁶. It has thus become a major figure in the research landscape in Gaza (fig.7).

The most impressive objects in his collection were exhibited in Geneva in 2007 at the Museum of Art and History; in parallel and through his enterprise, he built his own Museum in Gaza, with the aim of making the history of Gaza accessible to its people¹⁷. This ambition was possible thanks to the support of French archaeologists who came to work on site for several months. His implication is one of the few barriers limiting the leak - however partially - of a large number of archaeological objects looted and sold, while government can't succeed to stop the leak, both by lack of staff and of financial support.

The question of identity is a crucial point concerning the inhabitants in Gaza. Most of them are living in terrible conditions, in which they have no past to strengthen them, nor future to hope for. Our duty, as archaeologists and historians, as diggers of the past, is to give to inhabitants an idea of their history, their cultural tradition through roots that can be relied on. In Gaza, the heirs of an incredibly glorious past are ignorant and not exactly interested in these considerations, because of their very heavy and complex situation. And this last point is, also, a consequence of the war.

3.2.2 Private Collection VS Archaeological Ethic

It is difficult to see the boundary of heritage preservation by private collection. Is it part of the duty, of archaeological ethic, to permit the buying of looted objects to avoid the leakage, if possible by authorities ; but if not, what's the choice? In Gaza, this question becomes meaningful, as well as for many other sites in the Middle East. At what moment is the limit reached? The collector who opened his doors saved some of the archaeological findings from Gaza but the plunder continues because the current conditions in Gaza do not allow the inhabitants to live decently enough to ignore the value of objects buried under their feet. The consequences of the conflict on the population supposes, in addition to the destruction of the sites destined to perish drowned under the concrete, the permanent leakage of archaeological objects towards buyers. This situation makes it necessary to reconsider the way in which rescues, whatever they may be, can be apprehended.

16. GUELPA 2009.

17. HALDIMANN *et al.* 2007 ; Opening of Gaza Museum, LEBHOUR 2008.

Figure 7: The Khoudary Personal Museum, Photo credit Alain Chambon, 2008.

CONCLUSION

Studying the history of Gaza takes the form of personal, intellectual and physical involvement. The archaeological wealth of the Gaza region, still not very much studied, is now more known by the objects that looting reveals than by scientific explorations. It is then necessary to look into these illegal excavations, and to create a local network to establish a documentary watch on heritage that may be sold outside the territory. This watch does not prevent the looting, but it allows to document at least partly objects that may otherwise disappear forever from the heritage of the region.

The various excavations that have been done in previous years have given rise to some publications, but much remains to be done. Much of the excavation documentation, now stored on site, is still under study. The continuation of this work requires an adaptation both to the political or military constraints and the material constraints related to the particular situation of this territory. The war situation requires great flexibility as well as a great rigor in the collection of information. The work

of gathering information is also accompanied by inventiveness to make up for the lack of study material. The gathering of information must be as complete as possible, because nothing allows to ensure the continuity of the missions. Even if incomplete, these data allow researchers, once they have returned from their stay, to use the data collected and to shed more light on the knowledge of this area.

It is then a personal commitment to the extent that the situation of war and the consequent blockade create a complex human situation. The human link is essential in that it also concerns private collections. It is a necessary relay for the conservation of a part of the archaeological artefacts otherwise doomed to disappear, and for the maintenance on the spot of a network of information on the human reality of the situation. It is thanks to these links that the research succeeds, despite the difficulties, to maintain a form of hope in a territory that no longer has any, to avoid the destruction of entire parts of history, but also to restore for Gazaeans their past.

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